

CRAFT Proposal: The Turing Way Guide to Ethical Research

Proposed Title

Open Communities for Ethical Data Science: The Turing Way Guide to Ethical Research.

Roles and Responsibilities

Coordinator(s)

Laura Carter (she/her), PhD candidate, University of Essex, UK, laura.carter@essex.ac.uk
(primary contact)

Malvika Sharan (she/her), Turing Way Community Manager, The Alan Turing Institute, UK,
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Presenter(s)

Laura Carter (she/her), PhD candidate, University of Essex, UK - presenter, group facilitator
(TBC, UTC+0 or UTC-5)

Malvika Sharan (she/her), Turing Way Community Manager, Alan Turing Institute, UK -
presenter, group facilitator (UTC+0)

Arielle Bennett (she/her), Research Project Manager, Alan Turing Institute, UK, group facilitator
(UTC+0)

An additional 2-3 members of the existing Turing Way community will join to help facilitate small groups (the composition will depend on the timing of the session: community members are on 5 continents).

Documenter

Malvika Sharan (she/her), Community Manager - The Turing Way, Alan Turing Institute, UK

Format:

Interactive workshop:

- Presentation: Introduction to the Turing Way (20 mins, Laura and Malvika)

- The Turing Way and the Alan Turing Institute
- The Guide to Ethical Research
- Open Leadership principles
- Code of Conduct for participation
- Breakout rooms: intro to GitHub, Markdown, HackMD (20 minutes)
 - (small groups with facilitated support either from experienced participants and/or Turing Way community members: we will run both written and spoken breakout rooms)
 - Intro to HackMD and Markdown
 - Creating a GitHub account (for those who don't already have one)
 - Intro to GitHub repositories and the Turing Way repository
- Hands-on session (130 minutes)
 - 30 minutes: Create a list of subtopics - aspects of ethical research
 - 10 minutes: In small groups (breakout rooms, written and spoken): discuss the aspects of ethical research: subtopics that you think researchers should know about, or areas where you want to learn more!
 - 10 minutes: Group report outs – “Cluster” bullet points on the HackMD
 - 10 minutes: Organise in groups of 4-6 by subtopics (facilitators to put people in breakout rooms, splitting groups into written/spoken if required)
 - 40 minutes: In small group breakout rooms, write bullet points and start to structure contributions
 - 30 minutes: Compile bullet points on the HackMD
 - 10 minutes: Group report outs – Shared insights
 - 30 minutes: Structuring and writing
 - 25 minutes: In breakout groups: open GitHub Issue based on the bullet points
 - 5 minutes: Group report outs: what did you do? What did you learn?
 - 30 minutes: Coworking Pomodoro
 - 25 minutes: Review other Github issues (or keep working on the one you created!), join breakout groups to discuss or work with others
 - 5 minutes: Report out
- Wrap-up (10 minutes)
 - Ensure everyone has access to notes and links
 - Promote future collaborate cafes and co-working events
 - Make sure all participants know how to access the Slack workspace and to sign up for the mailing list

Length

3 hours

Summary/programme blurb

The Turing Way is an open source book project that involves and supports a diverse research community in ensuring that reproducible and ethical data science is accessible and comprehensible for everyone. This session will introduce participants to the Turing Way book project, its ethos and the practical tools to involve new contributors in its community efforts.

Description

Responsible, reproducible and ethical research is a journey, not a destination. It is also both an individual and collective responsibility: everyone involved in research should be aware of what power they have and what actions they can take to push data science work towards being more responsible, inclusive and ethical.

The Turing Way is an open source community-driven guide to reproducible, ethical, inclusive and collaborative data science. The goal of the project is to

- provide a resource for information that data scientists in academia, industry, government and the third sector need at the start of their projects to ensure that their work is reproducible and ethical throughout.
- Build a community of researchers who learn from each other and share knowledge, support and experience.

The Turing Way is built on Mozilla's Open Leadership principles of understanding, sharing, and participation and inclusion. We are committed to creating a space where people with diverse expertise and lived experiences can share their knowledge with others to allow us all to use data science to improve the world.

This session will introduce participants to The Turing Way community. By the end of the session, participants will:

- Know what information and resources are already available in the Turing Way book
- Have contributed to the open-source book project: we will take participants through the process of adding suggestions and content to the book, including an introduction to the main tools (GitHub and Markdown) that are used for contributions
- Know how to join the community for support and sharing knowledge

Additional artifacts (optional)

- The Turing Way is online here: <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/welcome.html>
- This session will draw on the material presented at a (shorter) session in Feb 2020
 - <https://zenodo.org/record/3706513> (slides)
 - <https://hackmd.io/HOLuUWtkR8GIT897djzc-g?both> (140 min session)

Primary Theme Your Session Fits Into

We think that this session fits within **Theme 3: Generating Higher Order Critiques** as it engages with ways to improve research processes.

Platform

We know that we can run the session using Zoom. If an alternative platform is preferred (e.g. for consistency with the rest of the programme), it will need to have:

- Screen sharing for all participants
- Breakout rooms that can be assigned manually (or that participants are free to choose from)
- Editable display names
- Ability to share clickable links

Target Audience Size

We can accommodate up to 30 participants in the session as planned and can scale this up if needed with additional facilitation support.

Documentation and Reporting Plans

We will document the session through:

- Tagging contributions to the book made during the session with a unique label (FAccT-2021)
- Ensuring the shared document that we use in the session is available to all participants during and after the session
- Making slides and other presentation materials open and accessible on Zenodo
- Producing a report (covering issues opened and contributions made) for the microsite

Publicity Plans

- We will promote the session using:
 - The Turing Way Twitter account @TuringWay, as well as personal Twitter accounts for the presenters @LauraC_rter
 - The Turing Way Slack workspace and newsletter, to reach existing contributors available to support or join the session
 - The existing hashtag
- The workshop will also be promoted as part of the Tools, Practices & Systems programme at the Alan Turing Institute and The Turing Way community via their

newsletters and Slack workspace. We will also encourage cross-posting in different communities to attract a wider audience.

Other Needs

We will take the following steps to increase accessibility for our session:

- We will use otter.ai to provide live transcription of the presentation
- We will organise breakout rooms and provide an option to choose between spoken or written discussion for participants based on their preference and comfort
- We will model pronoun display in our usernames to respectfully address people and explain to participants how to do this should they wish
- Participation in the event will be governed by the existing Turing Way Code of Conduct (please see: <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/community-handbook/coc.html>) as well as any code of conduct put in place by the FAcct conference organisers. In the event that there is any conflict between these codes of conduct, Laura and Malvika will discuss how to resolve these with the CRAFT co-chairs.

Laura and Malvika will also be happy to discuss other specific or general adjustments required to accommodate people with different accessibility needs.